

CATEGORIES OF SPECIAL CASES OF THE FRENCH LANGUAGE LEXICAL AND PHRASEOLOGICAL DESCRIPTION

Nigorabonu Nizomiddinovna Suvonova

Docent, candidate of philological sciences

Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Tel: +998937280438 / snigorabonu@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the lexical and phraseological means of expression of the case category are revealed on the example of the French language. In particular, the differential and non-differential characteristics of the semantic relations between the word expressing the situation and the phraseological unit were analyzed, and as a result, the functional types of such lexical units were determined.

In linguistics, the problem of words representing the status category was first addressed by A.Kh. Vostokov, A.A. Developed by Shakhmatov, L.V.Sherba and V.V.Vinogradov. The words expressing the situation and their interpretation between the word groups are distinguished from the words of other groups by their own characteristics. It is known that the problem of word groups has been studied by linguists for thousands of years, but no definite conclusion has been reached regarding their classification.

In linguistics, adverbs have the same status as other words. However, they are distinguished by their grammatical, semantic and functional features compared to words belonging to other word groups. Verbs, nouns, adjectives, and adverbs are a group of words that reflect the status category. That's why in linguistics, some people call the words expressing the situation verbs, while others call them short adjectives with the meaning of verbs, or nouns and adverbs. called zal. In addition, they are explained by other terms such as predicative adverbs, impersonal predicative words, predicatives. But some linguists study the words expressing the situation separately without including them in any word group. V.V. Vinogradov includes the words expressing the situation in the group of invariable words and states that they are expressed by the infinitive in participles and one-component sentences.

In French, as in other languages, the words expressing the status category serve to indicate the qualitative state of a certain person or object. In this case, under the concept of a qualitative state, the concepts of the state that occurred in the process of movement or occurred in the process of describing a certain object are reflected.

In the process of researching the means of expression of the case category in the French language, it is appropriate to divide them into two large structural groups, that is, lexical units with one element and two or more elements. In this case, adverbs, verbs, adjectives, nouns, and adjectives can be included in the one-element lexical units representing the state, and

phraseological units, phrases, and adverbs can be included in the two-element lexical units. Let's pay attention to the following structure-table in order to express this opinion more clearly:

It is known that the words expressing the situation are always Comment ? De quelle façon?, De quelle manière ? there will be an answer to the question. However, according to the explanation given above, taking into account that the words belonging to the noun and verb word groups also have a case category, such words belong to the noun and verb Qu'est-se qui ? , Qu'est-se que? or Que faire? there may be answers to your questions. The French verbs craindre, se fatiguer or nouns such as la tranquillité, la joie also have a certain level of state meaning in their semantic meaning.

The case category is reflected through single-element lexical units in French, often through words belonging to the adverbial word group. They, in turn, are actualized in speech with the help of pure idioms and artificial idioms that express the situation.

In French, adjectives, in particular present and past adjectives, are considered as one of the means of expressing the category of situation in the language. Since the formation process of adjectives is related to verbs, the stative feature of verbs is considered transferred to adjectives. For example:

- Present participle: J'ai lu "La Belle dormante".
- Past participle: Le tableau accroché au mur est très grande.

Taking into account the fact that verbs always express action, state and process in traditional grammar, it is necessary to pay attention to the presence of situational verbs among the lexical-semantic types of verbs. In addition, V. G. Gak also emphasizes that verbs in French are divided into dynamic and stative verbs from the lexical-semantic point of view. Therefore, stative verbs in the French language can be considered as one of the next means of expressing the status category. For example: Je me suis fatigué. Nous effrayeons. Il rougit.

The lexical units representing the above-mentioned status category are one-element means, which are widely used in modern French grammar to express the meaning of status.

In French, the second large group of actualization tools of the case category consists of language units with two or more elements. First of all, these include phraseological units,

word combinations, and adverbs, since their construction consists of two parts. In this case, verb and adverbial phraseological units are among the most productive means of expressing the status category in the language. As a proof of our opinion, let's pay attention to the following examples:

French phraseological units expressing status:	
<i>à pas feutres</i>	<i>mourir á petit feu</i>
<i>à boulets rouges</i>	<i>à grosses gouttes</i>
<i>à gorge déployée</i>	<i>en sabots</i>
<i>mettre en peine</i>	<i>être sous les armes</i>

A.G. Nazaryan considers the adverbial phraseological units that act as a case in modern French as non-predicative adverbial phraseological units and divides them into dependent and non-subordinated units. For example, *à toute force* – with all his might (subordinate); *à peine* – barely (no subjunctive). Most non-subordinate phrases are called locutions prépositives in French, but they can also be considered partial FBs: *à charge de / à partir de / à défaut de / à fin de / à l'effet de / à même de / à peine de / sous peine de / etc.*

In its historical development during the transition from synthetic construction to analytical construction, the French language gradually acquires new elements of analytical construction. The use of articles considered as an analytical construction element is generally limited within certain periods. At the present time, it is observed that articles are dropped in the phraseological units that we are studying: *à poings fermes*, *à gorge déployée*, *à bride abattue*, *à boulevue*, *à tombeau ouvert*, *à main fermée*, *à pas feutres*, *à dépêche compagnon* etc.

Another type of units representing the status category in French phraseology is phraseological units with verbs. When they are analyzed semantically, some different features are visible. In particular, such verb phraseological units can be divided into two groups according to the semantic meaning they represent. That is, phraseological units expressing a pure state and expressing a state through action. Phraseological units that express a state through action are further divided into several types: phraseological units that express a state through physical action, phraseological units that express a state through speech activity, and phraseological units that express a state through mental activity. For example:

FBs representing pure state:

Être enrhumé comme un loup- to catch a cold very hard;

FBs that express state through action:

Faire des yeux de basilic - to look with the eyes of hatred;

Free phrases in the French language are also one of the actualization tools of the status category. They are often realized through the conjunction *comme* based on comparatives, the preposition *sans*, and word combinations with various subordinate relations. For example:

Using the preposition *-sans* - *Il va sans hésiter.*

With the conjunction *-comme* - *Il courait comme un lapin*

using the phrase - *Ils se regardèrent d' un air étonné.*

Adverbs in the French language are also one of the forms of expression of the status category in the language. For example:

Il attendit, en écoutant la musique. "Oui," dit Pierre en souriant.

Summarizing the above-mentioned opinions about FBs expressing state in French, they can be expressed more clearly through the following structural scheme:

The words expressing the situation and their interpretation between the word groups are distinguished from the words of other groups by their own characteristics. It is known that the problem of word groups has been studied by linguists for thousands of years, but no definite conclusion has been reached regarding their classification.

In the process of researching the means of expression of the case category in the French language, they can be divided into two large structural groups, that is, lexical units with one element and two or more elements. In this case, adverbs, verbs, adjectives, nouns, and adjectives can be included in the one-element lexical units representing the state, and phraseological units, phrases, and adverbs can be included in the two-element lexical units.

In French, all idioms in the function of case (le complément circonstanciel de manière) are considered to be one of the most basic tools that reflect the category of case in the language.

In the French language, the words expressing the status category are widely distributed among the noun, verb, adjective and adverb word groups, and each of them is distinguished by its own structural-semantic features. In addition, in comparison with simple lexemes, higher lexical units, that is, word combinations and phraseological units, are considered to be the main means of expression of the status category in the language.

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